

UKCEH DRI Futures: understanding attitudes, experiences and expectations

Authors:

David Green

Affiliation:

UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology

Contents

About this work	3
Summary	3
Rationale for the work	3
Methodology	4
Lessons learnt	5

About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

DRI Futures is a programme of participatory research and co-design, led by the Environmental Data Science team at the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (UKCEH). It focuses on Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) for environmental science. DRI includes a wide variety of tools and technologies, which are often combined and used in different ways. The aim of the programme is to understand different attitudes, experiences and expectations of DRI, and to develop DRI with enhanced functionality, and aligned to progressive data science principles such as 'FAIR' (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable). There are many opportunities, as well as practical and operational challenges around developing, maintaining, and supporting DRI. DRI Futures is using co-creation to obtain user-centred insights into these opportunities and challenges. The programme launched in 2023 with an online survey, a series of interviews, and four co-design workshops, focused internally at UKCEH and with next steps to explore wider engagement externally.

Rationale for the work

The aims of DRI Futures are to explore ways to improve DRI so that it can better meet the needs of environmental science now and in the future; to identify opportunities to embrace new and emerging digital capabilities; to support the collaboration of stakeholders in environmental science; and to provide environmental data scientists with the right tools.

Methodology

DRI Futures involved three elements - a survey, interviews and workshops. The DRI Futures survey aimed to establish an overview of stakeholder needs across UKCEH, while the interviews provided a space for dialogue and a more in-depth understanding. The workshops were designed to explore three DRI strategic priorities for UKCEH: (i) How DRI supports collaborative environmental science by embodying the four FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Re-usability), (ii) the environmental sustainability of DRI, (iii) the skills and support needed to maximise the impact and value of DRI. Workshops took place (in-person) at the four main UKCEH sites (Wallingford, Edinburgh, Lancaster, and Bangor). Each workshop adopted a consistent format, framed around 2 key activities: a 50-minute *mapping* exercise and a 50-minute *design* exercise.

To give a flavour of the design for these workshops, we have detailed below the mapping and design exercises for the FAIR workshop.

- For the ***mapping exercise***, participants were separated into small groups and invited to take 10 minutes to think about the idea of FAIR assets and note down thoughts on Post-It notes around the following prompts: Assets; Experiences; Feelings; Opportunities; Challenges. Participants then collated these thoughts on a group 'map', which was consolidated into new themes, which were then annotated. Groups then reported key points from the map with the whole workshop
- For the ***design exercise***, participants were asked to use the themes from the mapping exercise to design a vision for collaborative environmental science at UKCEH. They were asked to consider any digital tools needed for FAIR assets, what attributes those tools would need, and any specific principles or standards for ontologies and vocabularies, governance processes for supporting FAIR assets and collaborative environmental science, etc. Discussion then focused on what would be needed to enable the design visions.

All data across the survey, workshop and interviews have been, or are currently undergoing analysis, in order to establish insights for the future direction of DRI. Insights from the data will be shared via papers. Insights have also been presented to various stakeholder groups within the organisation for supporting next steps, such as the teams working on skills support, DRI development, and data stewardship. A focused analysis of the data, supported by NERC, led to a report, '[DataLabs and Discoverability](#)' that analysed how discoverability might be better supported by DataLabs (an online virtual lab platform, provided and supported by UKCEH).

Lessons learnt

There are many opportunities for DRI Futures to expand and develop, through partnerships and expanding the lines of inquiry beyond UKCEH into the wider environmental science community. But, as well as the insights for future DRI, we also learned lessons from the process itself. These include:

Co-creation is an ongoing process: Activities such as DRI Futures take time to design, recruit for, conduct, analyse, reflect upon, and disseminate. While this, as a phase of the co-design process, had clear objectives, the 'DRI Futures' programme continues apace, with several new phases proposed for 2025/26 that build upon, extend, and focus on particular aspects.

Co-creation is about listening as well as doing: Many impressions of co-creation and co-design focus on practical making and the production of artefacts. However, this is only part of the picture. Many conceptualisations of co-design (e.g. Design Thinking) have a strong focus on understanding people, challenging assumptions and redefining problems.

Co-creation has many facets: This phase of DRI Futures used several methods in parallel; a study, interviews, and workshops. These were all selected for the particular qualities they bring to the process. The survey was intended to be wide and shallow, whereas the interviews were more focused and went deeper. The workshop focused on cross-pollinating ideas through dialogue between participants.

Co-creation needs facilitation: Workshops are an excellent way to bring people together, but they need to be carefully designed and facilitated to make sure that everyone feels included and everyone's voice can contribute. It was important to create a safe and inclusive space; this informed our decision to hold workshops in person and at each of the four UKCEH sites.

Thank you to the participants for their time and enthusiasm, as well as to all the organising team who were involved in the first round of DRI Futures.